

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

IS “STRATEGY OF MANAGER” EFFECTIVE UNDER STRESS?

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Abstract

The aim of the work is evaluating self-regulation strategies under stress that reflect the adaptive mechanisms of a person and describe the possibilities of using game biofeedback training to develop effective skills. Game biofeedback technology was used. Effective self-regulation strategies is considered to be an essential factor in achieving high results, as well as one of the important aspects in maintaining the health.

Keywords: biofeedback game, strategy of self-regulation, physiological expenditures, stress-resilience.

By learning to cope with difficult life circumstances and plan one's actions in the uncertain, unstable conditions, a person has permanent mental and physical stress. There is a need to have at hand effective tools/technologies and know how to use them. These technologies are based on an individual's ability to organize psycho-physiological resources in optimal way, on “self-regulation”.

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In our previous studies we developed an inventory to evaluate the effectiveness of self-regulation ability under stress conditions based on heart rate (HR) biofeedback game (“Vira-Rally” test). Stress conditions were simulated as car racing game “Rally” or diving competition “Vira” where the speed of players inversely depended on their heart rate (HR), and they had to react fast to random objects. Six strategies of self-regulation were identified differentiating by their efficiency.

There was a classification of strategies of self-regulation offered by our authors (Mazhirina, Jafarova, Pervushina, 2010, 2012):

№ 1. Trials and errors strategy with positive result. This strategy involved losing in several trials but achieving the goal in the end. **№ 2. Strategy of demotivation.** This strategy involved achieving the goal during first part of the training session and consequently, the results impaired during second part. **№ 3. Strategy of successive impairment of results.** This strategy involved individual's inability to fulfil the task. **№ 4.**

Strategy of successive learning. This strategy involved achieving positive results with each consecutive trial. **№ 5. Pendula strategy.** This strategy involved alternation of successful and non-successful trials. **№ 6. Non-integrated strategy (NIS).** This strategy involved the individual's ability to fulfil only one of the tasks (to control either reaction time (RT) or HR in “Rally” and keep HR unchanged in “Vira”). Based on the effectiveness of the achieved results and the ability to change during further biofeedback training, all strategies of self-regulation were divided into: effective (№1, №4), non-effective (№2, №6), and ‘intermediate’ (№3, №5), - (Jafarova, et.al., 2010, Mazhirina, Jafarova, 2011, 2012).

The non-integrated strategy (NIS) was defined as ineffective and difficult to be improved by further biofeedback training. Nevertheless, it was revealed that this strategy, especially in “Rally” game, which appeared very frequent, was not homogeneous, as about 20% of all participants demonstrated the following behavior pattern during the assessment session: they had high efficiency of RT control and low ability to regulate inter-beat interval (IBI); and about 10% had a controversial strategy: they increased IBI duration and could not control RT.

The aim of our study was to find out if there were any differences in these subgroups and to make a decision whether both of them were maladaptive and could not be changed during the biofeedback training.

Method

145 students of the Novosibirsk Regional Fire-fighter Training Center of EMERCOM of Russia took part in playing the “Rally” game in a course of stress resilience training in 2013-2015. All of them were males of 25 ± 6 years old. The behavior of 43 of them resembled the NIS mentioned above (30 subjects who

controlled RT formed group 1, 13 subjects who controlled HR formed group 2). These 43 students became the subjects of the study.

The strategy of Group 1 was named as Strategy 7 and was described as a “Strategy of a manager”, who had to fulfil the duty in any case.

The strategy of Group 2 has kept the name № 6. Non-integrated strategy. The groups were balanced in age.

Assessment

Pic. 1. Example of 7 (left) and 6 (right) strategy.

Biofeedback Procedure

In our experimental study we used 2 games: «Vira» and «Rally». The game «Vira» is a competition of two on-screen divers to get treasures from the sea bottom. The task is to win by controlling the speed of one of the divers during the game trial. The game results reflect the ability to relax intentionally by slowing down a player’s pulse.

The game “Rally” is a race of two cars, where the speed of a player inversely depends on his HR, and he has to react to random objects as quickly as possible.

Both games represented psycho-physiological model of stress (sports competition). During biofeedback sessions, IBI and RT data were recorded. All participants underwent testing session that included six trials of Vira followed by five trials of Rally.

Results

Groups differed in emotional and behavioral coping styles (see Table 1), but anxiety scores were close

We studied coping strategies (E.Heim questionnaire, 1988), style of behavioral self-regulation (V. Morosanova, 2001), anxiety (STAI), tolerance to ambiguity (MSTAT), and performed heart variability (HRV) analysis on the IBI probe of 300 beats conducted before “Vira-Rally” test performing. The whole testing procedure took about 3 hours and was held in the groups of 10-15 students. Usually, a subject (player) received the information about the assessing methods but not about the training procedure.

to normal values. So, we cannot correlate any weak results in IBI (RR) regulation with psychic tension that can be expressed as anxiety.

The comparison of HRV results analysis in both groups can give us a cue why it has happened.

For analysis, we used normalized values of HF and LF to avoid individual biases according to the formulas below:

$$HF (\%) = HF / (HF + LH + VLF), LF (\%) = LF / (HF + LH + VLF),$$

here we used conventional abbreviations for HRV analysis in frequency domain.

According to the results shown in Table 1, we can assume that the higher value of LF/HF index in the group with Strategy 7 is related to the sympathetic activation, and therefore, to the excessive expenditures of physiological resources in order to achieve the goal.

Results of One-way ANOVA. Total Model. Factor= Strategy.

Table 1.

Dependent variables, observed means	Factor ‘Strategy’		F	p
	Str 6	Str 7		
Anxiety state, STAI	32.60	34.10	0.23	0.631
Anxiety trait, STAI	30.80	31.40	0.72	0.400
Cognitive Coping, Heim	0.62	0.78	0.00	0.987
Emotional Coping, Heim	1.50	1.89	4.40	0.043
Behavioral Coping, Heim	1.00	1.36	4.05	0.049
HF %	34.12	28.65	8.54	0.006
LF %	38.07	45.93	6.84	0.012
LF/HF	1.21	2.16	19.16	0.001

At LF-HF scatterplot one can see the different interrelationship of LH and HF in the subgroups. The group with Strategy 7 had higher reactivity of ANS than the group with Strategy 6 where the vagal balance was presented. It confirmed our assumption of heterogeneity of the NIS strategy. Moreover, we found out that the

sub-subgroup with Strategy 7 that is circled with green color in the scatterplot not only had the predominance of sympathetic system but were significantly less independent according to Morosanova test than other subjects of Strategy 7 group (3.7 against 5.1; $F=3.98$, $p=0.048$).

Pic. 2. Scatterplot the different interrelationship of LH and HF in the subgroups.

The last aim of our study was to check if Strategy of a manager can be changed by biofeedback without psychotherapeutic intervention. Both groups conducted 7 sessions of Vira and Rally self-regulation training (30 min, 2-3 times a week).

It was shown that the strategy when one controlled only RT could be improved (83,3%) in contrast to Strategy 6 group where only 1 of 13 subjects (7,6 %) improved his self-regulation skills. The major changes may take place due to the active use of the biofeedback cognitive components.

Conclusion

Our study showed that when a person was trying to complete a given task in the most efficient way possible (assuming their best ability), the “**Strategy of manager**” lead to an excessive expenditures of physiological resources. However, it can be corrected by utilizing a psycho-physiological training. We could find the targets for a counselor/ biofeedback practitioner to work with, and increased stress resilience. Game biofeedback technology can help mastering the skills of self-regulation and preventing stress-related disorders.

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